

**The Macroeconomic and Microeconomic Challenges of the COVID-19 Pandemic:
A Case Study of Pakistan**

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to assess the COVID 19 pandemic by assessing its impact on Pakistan's macroeconomic and microeconomic impacts in emergency and panic environments. Over 190 countries around the world have been affected by COVID 19, and the pandemic virus is disrupting the economic system. In addition to this study, case studies were conducted specifically in developing countries and Pakistan. These data are collected from the official website of the Government of Pakistan and published by PIDE (Pakistan Institute for Development Economics) and Ministry of Health. This study covers the impact of COVID 19 on macroeconomic and microeconomic levels of Pakistan's view. The results show that GDP declines and poor health systems are shocking, with 0.75% health care and 0.6 hospital beds (per 1,000 people). It is the sixth most populous nation in the world, with poor literacy, exponential growth, and behaviour.

Keywords: macroeconomic, microeconomic, panic environments

JEL Codes: F62, O12

1. Introduction

This COVID 19 pandemic was confirmed in Wuhan, a densely populated city in China, on December 17th. In the past, 13 cities in China have been closed and blocked for education and transportation. During the panic, it was reported that more than 5 million people in China had the disease. In addition to the world, 14 million cases have been reported in 188 countries/regions. More common symptoms such as cough, fever, decreased taste, and difficulty breathing. People's gatherings and conversations are restricted. The World Health Organization (WHO) said it will keep people away from society and maintain frequent awareness of the virus and possible compliance with handwashing. At the global level, WHO first laid the foundation for the need to raise public awareness of the risks of isolation, communication and being at home, and to demonstrate compliance by the international community in emergencies (Ahorsu et al., 2020). Global medical emergencies are the primary target of diagnosis, treatment and vaccines. Key elements of public awareness March 7th WHO divided the country into four categories: the first category are no cases, the second category is unconventional cases and the third category, the fourth category clusters, the fourth is public broadcast, and 20 is spent on laboratories and medical equipment. One hundred million dollars.

In Pakistan, most hospitals have a low rate of comparing patient availability with ventilators. The population of Pakistan's younger generation has fallen by 64% under the age of 30. The budget utilization rate for health problems is 0.06% compared to the total population. Significant impacts on the growth of developing countries have currently been observed. The impact of the reflection on industry and manufacturing will have a significant impact on growth levels. Depending on the economic level, each country's economy plays an essential role in the development of the country. China will limit the vacuum of imports and exports and grant any form of access to prohibited substances that create uncertainty in the company's ability to conduct business. Countries can compete in this environment with the working environment, gender equality and employment opportunities. According to special CPEC considerations, Pakistan needs a lot of manpower and manpower in the industry to complete these projects quickly and quickly. One parameter is the poverty line and the other is the social distance, which is a very difficult situation for Pakistan's economy. Pakistan's economy now needs a lot of money. The blockade and panic affected the goods needed for investment work and all other types of logistics. Surgical masks, poor health facilities, a lack of awareness, and demand for high poverty rates are reversing Pakistan's economy.

2. Literature Review

The outbreak of COVID-19 affected all parts of the world. Whether for business or academic events. This global pandemic has destroyed everything. It is difficult for policymakers to develop credible guidelines for the future, including Covid-19 response. Global currency markets are declining and so are the risks of a financial crisis. The (IMF) has identified some new speculation about 2020 actions (February 2020). Meet the expectations at the time of revision. The basis of the initial assessment is that the virus becomes a pandemic and most modest actions will eliminate at least 2.4% of its t(GDP) value in 2020. Estimates of global distress in late 2019, projected to reach \$87.7 trillion by 2020 However, estimates are much higher due to the impact of embedding and locking conditions.

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The Pakistan National Bank (SBP) report dated 10 March 2020 provides a new package, and it is expected that approximately (\$630.5 million) will be allocated to the health and sustainable sector. And when the Pakistani government announced that the EHASS plan to support poor families and the prime minister of the Republic of Pakistan would resolve the intolerable blockade of severe poverty, it would indicate all of the macro or macroeconomic impacts of the economy on the macroeconomy. The profound implications are discussed at the level of. MMQ, Vo, XH and Zaman, K. (2020).

The coronavirus and its fears have shaken businesses and affected the health of the global economy. Analysts worry that the situation may get worse because it is not expected to improve immediately (Brady et al., 2020). Macro and micro economic issue are very important for an economy (Ali and Senturk, 2019; Ali and Zulfiqar, 2018; Ali et al., 2016; Ali et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2021; Ali et al., 2015; Arshad and Ali, 2016; Ashraf and Ali, 2018; Audi and Ali, 2017; Audi and Ali, 2017; Audi et al., 2021; Ali and Ali, 2016). Large amounts of foreign investment in government bonds (called hot money) have also been leaked. There are large amounts both internationally and domestically. This is why it has not had the most serious impact. The health alert, especially in South Asia, is still very poor, and the availability of sanitation and isolation policies is simultaneously affected by poverty and weak medical care (Hamza et al., 2020). Similarly, Marmon and Ulla, Massachusetts (IM, 2020), countries with strong medical environments have limited treatment of diseases, so they Providing health care to citizens is a real challenge (Socherabi et al., 2020). As of mid-March 2020, the World Health Organization has made the virus a pandemic, and the International Monetary Fund is relaxing on Pan et al., 2020). In various progress situations, riding some initial diseases at the cost of the COVID-19 outbreak.

The shock wave is not only a demand management issue but also a complex crisis that requires revisions to financial, taxation and health policies (Paital et al., 2020; Roussel et al., 2021; Senturk and Ali, 2021; Sajid and Ali, 2018). Completing an exaggerated community interface is effective rework. The long-term comeback is even more important. Countries where many infectious diseases can occur. Experts continue to warn and warn that zoonotic diseases can continue to threaten the lives of millions of people and cause significant damage to the world's integrated economy. The latest COVID-19 proves that any country can be a clue for joining a small island in the global economic system Nicola et al., (2020).

3. The impact of the pandemic on the macroeconomy

The spread of viruses affects the world economy in three basic ways. In other words, the lack of chain organization. This has a direct impact on the direct impact on world population. On the other hand, the procurement market is facing a crisis due to the blockade without transport due to the worsening pandemic. The third is on the demand side, the panic situation in these countries is more severe and supply bottlenecks will be faced with financial crises and market collapses. In a study by Wildersmith et al., (2020) found that most of the world depends on China's industrial chains and economic conditions, as China is one of the countries offering this service. I pointed out that I do. We provide products and services to the world in an inexpensive manner. Traffic regulations lack flaws in the global economy. Limited or even restricted countries have limited financial markets and slow down global macroeconomic activity. Most importantly, the panic-induced differences between companies have distorted the usual solid outlines and distorted market differences. The establishment of Chinese goods and chain stores in Pakistan and many developing countries, as well as the panic in other countries, are increasing (especially when supply curves are volatile in the short term). Is the inability to find quantities and ingredients. Source (Wang Q., Su, M. (2020). The second major part of the impact is due to supply-side interference and the closure of work units and housing. Consumers reduce spending and secret demand. Shift curves and reduce GDP (Spinelli, A. & Pellino, G. (2020). Massive expansion is due to the lack of product chain imbalances that have been spent managing supply chains and demand departments Ranney et al., 2020; Nasir et al., 2021). The ability to manage people and meet their daily needs is stronger than any other country with a Chinese economy, including the United States. Manage a global brute force flow of goods and services and you can stimulate these without raising prices. Mission in the world: In addition to China is t the short-term investment behaviour of investors has gotten stronger, and giant investors around the world are again short-term spam with the Chinese market. (Jan et al., 2020) The most affected companies are the tour companies who hope tourism will be the engine of economic growth (Chakraborty, I. and Maity, P. (2020)) We have been affected by the dependence on large-scale movements and gatherings, and these events and gatherings have been banned The stock market has never reached this low level. The index is now down 39.7% from its high to now stand at 21%. It survives to retreat with little investment.

This reduces the profitability of the banking sector. Foreign investors have withdrawn from all sectors of Pakistan. This has led to a decline in Pakistan's GDP. In Pakistan and calm conditions, GDP will be hit by countries in the 3-6% range. The sudden closure of large and small businesses has closed most of the economic centres, thereby hampering the entire economy. Export-related industries, production, and service industries were closed. Exports and foreign trade have fallen to death levels. This has led to a decline in GDP. The number of unemployed persons

in the United States exceeds 40 million, increasing from 6.2 million in February to 20.5 million in May 2020. This is a major depression in American history. My life is suddenly short. This COVID-19 pandemic has made daily betting broker intermediaries a great success.

Source: www.tradingeconomics.com

The United States has introduced important new things and new cases into the channels of global public utilities. Compared with different countries that constitute economic centres, more than 60% of chain stores in the world rely on them. According to the World Health Alert says that the pandemic has caused serious conditions and Dilemma. The emergency department is suffering from a huge infectious disease. Develop adjustments to weaker brands in most environments. According to Cowling et al., (2020). Social distance and other sectors are completely affected and cause distance (Anser et al.,2020). Due to the weak maintenance of prices in the integration of raw materials, production and demand factors worldwide are affected. Chan & Yuen (2020) stated that the domestic production capacity of surgical masks and other medical equipment is a question mark for developing countries. Due to the pandemic, the internal relations of other countries are not available.

4. The outbreak of coronavirus in the Pakistani economy

According to the Asian Development Bank, a large part of GDP depends on domestic and international income and business, as well as on the internal and external circulation of money (Fernandes, N. (2020)). Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX) Unfortunately, a serious panic of around 400 billion rupees in April 2020 resulted in foreign investment behaviour and expected losses being minimal. The first crisis is an estimate of GDP reduction in a poem scenario. PM In the Islamic Republic of Pakistan, we disagree with the lockdown due to poverty and the country's expectations for reverse growth, but there is a small state lockdown. Most daily wages in Pakistan are below the poverty line.

5. Research method based on the content analysis approach

This study is qualitatively based on case studies and phenomena. In this study, we used a content analysis approach. Data was collected from various reports on official websites and newspapers. The health-related issues and status discussed in this study are from the World Health Organization (WHO). The graph of Pakistan's budget and GDP decline comes from the official report of the pandemic of COVID 19 by PIDE (Pakistan Institute for

Economic Development) at the beginning of municipalities related to health issues, and the case of COVID 19 is a provincial state. Health Services, Regulations and Coordination (nhrc.gov.pk) and internally covered and formally confirmed by the Asian Development Bank.

Table 1

Years	GDP Growth Rate	Increase	Decrease	Economic Growth(USD)	Increase	Decrease
2016	5.53%	0.8%		\$278.69B	2.99%	
2017	5.55%	0.03%		\$304.57B	9.3%	
2018	5.84%	0.28%		\$314.57B,	3.28%	
2019	0.99%		4.85%	\$278.22B		11.55%

Source: Pakistan Institute of Development Economics (PIDE) Survey Report

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that Pakistan is one of the countries most affected by the virus, with its growth rate and GDP on the other side of the IMF. This money can be spent on addressing this declining GDP and emergency health care. For Pakistan to overcome poverty and the country in terms of support, it must be possible to use ventilators and specialists. The most powerful factor in the world is the global negative economy at the scale of the shocking consequences of COVID 19. Developed countries with more reserves need to work with the countries that have been hit hardest. At present, the economy is a dilemma for developing as well as developed countries. Pakistan is one of the countries with poor health care and few developing countries, and the pandemics of these viruses are higher than in India and other neighbouring countries other than Iran. The peak of viruses and infections is 8-10 months longer due to the maintenance and construction of business and trade. Every state district must have a highly effective channel for disinfectant supply chains and the implementation of SOPs at the state and interstate levels. There is a powerful and efficient way to understand the status of information through domestic healthcare and collaboration with other countries. In all financial markets, there is an important part of COVID 19 at the global macro level, but due to its strong previous level, GDP and growth rates are once again sustainable through the application of SOPS. But in the context of Pakistan, it is in developing countries, the country that is very poor and suffers the most. The IMF and the World Health Organization need to mitigate and support developing countries so they can compete on the poverty line.

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